

ANTIFUNGAL RESISTANCE: CURRENT TRENDS AND FUTURE STRATEGIES

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ABSTRACT

Due to the small number of systemically accessible antifungal medications, antifungal resistance poses a significant therapeutic issue for clinicians treating invasive fungal diseases. Additionally, drug-drug interactions and major side effects/toxicities may be a limitation of existing medications, preventing continued use or dosage escalation. Due to the rising occurrence of infections brought on by these species in various parts of the world and the higher prevalence of resistance to this widely used azole in many institutions, fluconazole resistance in non-*Candida albicans* species is of special concern. It has been shown that *C. glabrata* resistance to echinocandins is increasing at a number of US institutions, and a greater proportion of these isolates may also be azole resistant. Worldwide, it has also been discovered that *Aspergillus fumigatus* isolates that are azole resistant can result in invasive infections with significant fatality rates due to clinical and environmental exposure to this class of drugs. Additionally, a number of *Aspergillus* species and other mould species, such as those of the genus *Scedosporium* and the genus *Fusarium*, have decreased susceptibility to or pan-resistance to clinically accessible antifungals. Several prospective antifungals, some of which have the ability to overcome resistance seen against the azoles and the echinocandins, are now undergoing preclinical or clinical research. These include substances that also target the formation of ergosterol and β -glucan as well as drugs with unique modes of action

that might also be able to get around the drawbacks of the currently known antifungal classes, such as resistance and negative side effects/toxicity. Very few drugs are used in veterinary practice. Hence much data is not available.

KEY WORDS

Antifungal drugs, Azoles, echinocandins, *Aspergillus*, *Candida albicans*, Resistance

INTRODUCTION

Clinicians responsible for treating patients at high risk for invasive mycoses are growing increasingly concerned about antifungal resistance. Following exposure to these medications, resistance to currently available antifungal medicines may emerge as a result of acquired mechanisms. Increased azole resistance among non-*Candida albicans* isolates, azoles resistance in *Aspergillus fumigatus*, and echinocandin resistance in *C. glabrata* are some recent developments in acquired antifungal resistance (1–3). Contrarily, some fungal species exhibit microbiologic resistance to all clinically available antifungals, while others are intrinsically resistant to specific medications (e.g., *C. krusei* and fluconazole or *C. lusitanae* and amphotericin B) (e.g., *Lomentospora* [formerly *Scedosporium*] *prolificans* and *Fusarium solani*). 4–6 Additionally, new species are appearing that may exhibit resistance to certain classes of already used medicines (e.g., *C. auris*)⁷. Treatment options for invasive fungal infections are limited, and patients at highest risk frequently have multiple comorbidities, including immun-

osuppression, which may limit the effectiveness of therapy even in the absence of drug resistance. This is true even though the prevalence of antifungal resistance is not at the levels observed for some bacteria against different antibiotics. In addition to overcoming the toxicities/adverse effects and drug interactions linked to currently available antifungals, which itself potentially restrict the efficacy of therapy, it is evident that novel treatment approaches are required to address this issue. Antifungal resistance is a problem, however several novel antifungals are being tested in both preclinical and clinical settings. This review's goal is to describe the most recent developments in antifungal resistance and new antifungals that are being tested in patients with invasive fungal infections both in preclinical and clinical settings. Numerous extracts from various plants, including isolates resistant to currently available antifungal medications, have also been demonstrated to have activity against various fungi. A thorough examination of medicinal plants and their extracts, however, is outside the purview of this article. effects/toxicity.

Non *C. albicans* resistance

Azole reactivity Although *C. albicans* is the most prevalent *Candida* species cultured from patients with candidiasis, infections brought on by other species within this genus, such as *C. glabrata*, *C. parapsilosis*, and *C. tropicalis*, are becoming more significant in various parts of the world. The species can also vary between different geographic regions. This is significant since research from numerous institutions and geographical areas has indicated that resistance is rising in many non-*C. albicans* species. 8–10 According to the World Health Organization, fluconazole resistance is more prevalent in species other than *Candida albicans*(11). This is concerning because fluconazole is an easily administered, reasonably priced, and well-tolerated oral drug. Because point mutations in the ERG11 gene, which encodes the enzyme lanosterol 14a-

demethylase, increase transcription of this gene, resulting in increased amounts of the enzyme, or efflux pumps, such as Cdr1 and Cdr2, which also affect this class of antifungals, reduce fluconazole susceptibility, it is possible that resistance to fluconazole also means resistance to other azoles (12,13).

As was previously mentioned, different geographic regions may have different predominant non-*C. albicans* species generating infections, and different institutions may have varying rates of azole resistance. Clinical practitioners' prescription habits for the prevention and treatment of invasive candidiasis may have an impact on this. 14 *C. glabrata* is the second most frequent cause of invasive candidiasis in the USA, and some institutions have been found to have fluconazole resistance rates as high as 12%–18%. 15,16 In contrast, *C. tropicalis* predominates in some Indian healthcare facilities, where fluconazole resistance rates might vary dramatically(17,18). In some Chinese hospitals, the prevalence of *C. parapsilosis* is comparable to that of *C. albicans* in terms of the quantity of isolates cultured from patients with invasive infections (19–22). Fluconazole susceptibility varies greatly amongst institutions as well, with some reporting no azole resistance and others reporting that the percentage of fluconazole-susceptible, dose-dependent plus resistant isolates in intensive care units may reach 50% (20,22).

Resistance to echinocandins

Due to the risk of resistance, echinocandins are recommended as the first line of therapy against invasive candidiasis in immunocompromised patients and those who have previously been exposed to azoles (23). Because their mechanism of action differs from that of azoles, echinocandins such as anidulafungin, caspofungin, and micafungin have been shown to maintain potent in vitro activity against many *Candida* isolates resistant to fluconazole and other triazoles(24). Resistance to echinocandins can develop in response to exposure to members of this

class, and this occurs through point mutations in highly conserved regions (i.e., hot spots 1 and 2) of the FKS1 and FKS2 genes, which encode subunits of the glucan synthase enzyme. 25 These hot spot regions are conserved across *Candida* species, and their detection in multiple species collected from patients who have experienced both microbiologic and clinical failure has been reported(26–28).

Candida isolates with multidrug resistance

Resistance to multiple drug classes is also an issue in some non-*C. albicans* species. According to one study publication, 11% of fluconazole-resistant bloodstream infections were also resistant to an echinocandin(29) More recently, an increase in echinocandin-resistant *C. glabrata* isolates (i.e., isolates classified as intermediate or resistant) was reported in a large surveillance study conducted in four large metropolitan areas in the United States. While these findings are consistent with single-center studies, a third of the isolates that were nonsusceptible to an echinocandin were also resistant to fluconazole in this multicenter surveillance study, which included over 1300 isolates, compared to only 8.1% of the isolates that were echinocandin susceptible. The exact cause of azole and echinocandin coresistance in some *C. glabrata* isolates is unknown due to differences in mechanisms of action and known mechanisms of resistance. Because many patients with *C. glabrata* invasive candidiasis have multiple comorbidities, prior exposure to these antifungal classes may also play a role. Furthermore, isolates with a disrupted MSH2 mismatch repair gene have a hypermutable phenotype, suggesting that they are more likely to produce multidrug-resistant mutants (30).

Aspergillus resistance

Recently, azole-resistant *Aspergillus* species, especially *A. fumigatus*, have gained attention. With extended clinical exposure, itraconazole, posaconazole, voriconazole, and isavuconazole resistance can develop in *Candida* species. This is well-documented and can oc-

cur in patients with persistent pulmonary aspergillosis who receive azole therapy for years. 39,40 Point mutations in the CYP51A gene, which encodes the Cyp51 enzyme, generate *A. fumigatus*' acquired resistance. Different mutations cause resistance to voriconazole and isavuconazole, posaconazole and itraconazole, and panazole(31–32).

The establishment of azole resistance in *A. fumigatus* is troublesome due to restricted therapeutic options. Amphotericin B and echinocandins can cure invasive aspergillosis, but each has limits. Amphotericin B deoxycholate is associated with clinically significant nephrotoxicity, which may limit its use. Nephrotoxicity can still occur, especially with higher doses or extended administration(33) Echinocandins avoid amphotericin B's toxicities, however they're not indicated as monotherapy for invasive aspergillosis. 55 Amphotericin B and echinocandins must be given intravenously, which can be troublesome for long-term therapy(34–35)

The common drug resistance mechanisms are alteration of drug efflux, alteration of the target enzyme, alteration of the *erg3* genes, alteration of the drug influx and many more similar to that of the antibiotic resistance

Frequency of mechanisms of resistance

Perea et al [36] studied matched sets of 20 fluconazole-susceptible and -resistant isolates from HIV-infected patients with oropharyngeal candidiasis, presumably treated with azoles. They found overexpression of efflux pumps in 85% of resistant isolates (the frequency of overexpression of CDR genes and the MDR1 gene was similar), amino acid substitutions in the target enzyme lanosterol demethylase in 58%-65%, and overexpression of the gene that encodes the enzyme in 35%-42%. Multiple mechanisms of resistance were found in 75% of resistant isolates. White et al. [37] addressed this question in a different way. They analyzed 38 random isolates, half resistant and half susceptible, and found overexpression of the CDR genes only in

(some) resistant isolates and correlated with resistance. Neither MDR1, FLU1, or ERG11 overexpression nor amino acid point mutations correlated with resistance or were found frequently in resistant isolates. The latter study [38] suggests that putative resistance mechanisms found in resistant isolates, except for CDR-encoded pumps, may not be responsible for the resistance and that additional mechanisms of resistance remain to be uncovered. Both studies suggested CDR1 and CDR2 may be coregulated, and both reported additional data on cross-resistance to other azoles, in addition to that previously described.

Alteration of drug efflux

Altering drug efflux is a bacterial resistance mechanism (e.g., in *S. pneumoniae* resistance to macrolide antibiotics (36). ATP-binding cassette transporters are known to produce drug resistance. These membrane-spanning proteins have 2 ATP-binding cytoplasmic domains (36, 37). *Candida* CDR genes are linked to azole resistance. At least 5 CDR genes (CDR1-5). CDR1 is a *Candida* and *Cryptococcus* transporter protein that transports azoles and other medicines (38, 39). Its structure is similar to human P-glycoprotein, which causes chemotherapeutic drug resistance. Sanglard and Albertson compared *C. albicans*' ability to collect fluconazole. In both trials, azole-resistant strains had lower fluconazole levels. Northern blots indicated a 10-fold increase in CDR1 mRNA, indicating overexpression. Parkinson et al. (40) described fluconazole accumulation in susceptible and resistant *C. glabrata* isolates. The resistant isolate accumulated less fluconazole due to energy-dependent drug efflux. *C. albicans* mutants with a CDR1 deletion are hypersensitive to fluconazole, itraconazole, ketoconazole, terbinafine, and amorolfine. Overexpressing CDR2 confers azole resistance. Double-disrupted CDR1 and CDR2 strains were more hypersusceptible (41). Fluconazole-resistant *C. albicans* overexpresses MDR1 (42, 43).

In conclusion, Several harmful fungi are

resistant to various antifungal drugs. Several new antifungals are under development that may be better than the current medications in overcoming antifungal resistance and avoiding unwanted effects and drug interactions. Preclinical and clinical investigations are needed to evaluate if these medicines can overcome microbiologic and clinical failure in antifungal resistance.

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